

Genre-Based Approach: Its Integration To Teach English Grammar In Constructing Sentences

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Abstract: This study aims to discuss how teaching and learning activities were carried out by using Genre-based in teaching English grammar in constructing sentences at SMA Negeri 1 Kota Ternate. This study was conducted to the 27 students of class XI language and culture. The research was designed into a qualitative approach by using the phenomenological method. To collect data, the researcher used the students' results of the test. Research findings reveal that more than 70% of the students were successful in identifying the language features of constructing sentences. The implementation of a genre-based approach to teaching English grammar gives a good contribution to the improvement of the students' proficiency in constructing sentences.

Index Terms: Genre-based approach, teaching and learning, English grammar

1 INTRODUCTION

The best practice in teaching grammar today is to incorporate it into writing skill. Therefore, teachers at the Senior High School must achieve the students' communicative ability including writing. Writing sometimes looks very difficult that influences students for being lazy in developing writing activities. One possible problem is the lack of specific genre writing throughout the curriculum that can affect students' scorers or performance in English tests even on small writing activities, and most of them expressing the difficulties towards their writing. The problem includes choosing the right vocabulary, arranging the correct structure depending on the topic or purpose of the paper, following the exact grammar rules, and integrating ideas. To make the students interest in the materials, the implementation the suitable genre in teaching writing is expected to make them understand to construct the sentences in producing paper. The integration of a wide array of genres that have multiple communicative functions is an essential component of sufficient textbooks and materials in foreign and second language education [1-3]. Therefore general based approach will be applied to make students are comfortable when constructing the sentences. It is also to hope that this method can increase and motivate the students' ability in creating sentences using the correct generic structure and lexicogrammatical features because it provides students with more opportunity to practice more about other English skill, promoting collaborative learning as well as helping students to more engaging to learning tasks. The application of a genre-based approach together as an alternative in a model called the process genre approach.

The results confirm that this dual approach works well if the writing cycle begins with a model, a description of critical linguistic features, a discussion of the social situation in which it occurs, and an analysis of the recommended rhetorical patterns of each genre. Student writing is then following the concept sequence in the process approach. [4]. In implementing the general-based approach, teachers should understand the text type first. The text types suggested in the curriculum such as recount narrative, descriptive new item, procedure, report, discussion, spoof, review, analytical exposition, hortatory exposition, and explanation. Each of the text types has its characteristics, social function, linguistic feature, and generic structure.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Genre-Based Approach

The genre-based approach is a model of teaching applied in western countries in the mid-1960s. The genre-based approach is a model of teaching used in western countries in the mid-1960s. A genre Based Approach was first implemented in London 1964 sponsored by the Nuffield Foundation, then practiced in the School Council, and directed by Halliday [5, 6]. "A Genre-Based Approach" was a genre theory in developing writing activities and its implementation in the teaching of English in Asia (China and Korea, Singapore), and also in Indonesia. The Genre-Based Approach model is used by the teachers in Indonesia, according to School-Based Curriculum are Building of the field (BKOF), Modelling of Text (MOT), Joint Construction of Text (JCT), and Independent Construction of Text (ICT). A Genre-Based Approach was first famous as the product approach, which was then replaced by a process approach. In 1980, a genre approach became famous along with the idea that student writing could be useful from studying various types of written texts. Teachers in China and Korea made a study to improve that this approach can affect students' competencies in learning languages. The genre-based approach is one model of learning that emphasizes how to construct text, in which starting from creating the sentence to be text. A genre-based approach was more emphasis on the relationship between text-genre and its context to help students to be more participating in their academic and professional environment and their wider society [7]. Here are some characteristics of the genre-based approach.

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First, the genre-based approach focuses on how the importance of exploring the social and cultural context of language uses in writing skill, especially in constructing sentences. The context decides the objective of a text; the overall structure of the text about language features and text features is often in the form of linguistic conventions [7]. This approach claims that students can only create a successful composition that is accepted by certain English-speaking discourse communities after they apply it in the context of the text into their writing task.

Second, this approach focuses on the immensity of the readers and the linguistic conventions that their writing must be followed or be accepted by the readers. According to this approach, every student who wants to join a specific English-speaking discourse community successfully, he or she must be able to produce texts that meet his readers' expectations regarding grammar, organization, and content (8).

Third, it underlines that writing is a social activity. This idea comes from the socio-cultural theory driven by Vygotsky (1978) [9]. According to this theory, knowledge is best constructed when participants collaborate, support each other to enhance new ways to form, create and reflect new knowledge. Toward this occasion, social communication and their participation in a group play an important role in developing new concepts. In writing classes, collaborative activities can help students to enhance their involvement in doing exchange activities and asking negotiations with more capable people such as colleagues and teachers. Improving writing activity in this way, as it is believed, can eliminate feelings of isolation that interfere with many students when writing and at the same time. Besides, it can help the students to have positive reinforcements about linguistic knowledge, contents, and ideas in compiling texts.

Fourth, writing instructions by using a genre-based approach looks beyond the subject of the subject, design process and linguistic forms to view text as an effort to converse with readers. This approach is related to teaching students how to use language patterns to achieve coherence and purposeful prose writing. The central belief is that "we don't just to write, we write something to achieve the goals" [10]. In this approach, the student writers are asked to consider the overall social objectives of the text into the account when writing text.

Fifth, this approach emphasizes the critical role of writer-reader interaction on a piece of writing [11]. Firstly, student writer in this approach is requested to specify or think about the intended and potential readers when writing to be able to select or anticipate appropriate content, language and levels of formality. He or she should always ask himself or herself some questions such as who will be my intended readers? Who might be interested in reading my text? What are their beliefs about a good piece of writing?, What are their levels of English proficiency? And what are their educational and cultural backgrounds? Etc. Similarly, readers when approaching the text should also ask themselves some questions such as for what purposes does this writer write this piece of writing? What is the writer's viewpoint when writing the text? What kinds of language features and organization does he/she use in the text? And etc. To recap, there always exists an interaction between the writer and its readers in the

form of written communication despite the absence of readers.

Sixth, the role of teachers in this approach is seen as authoritative rather than authoritarian [12]. As an expert in the classroom, the teacher provides students with systematic guidance and active support through various activities for them to finally master the written genres. At the same time, he or she also aware of the importance of student's contributions to the teaching and learning process.

Last but not least, a genre-based approach emphasizes the explicit teaching of the genre in linguistic conventions for target language of student writers (Christie, 1990) [13]. It is said that students cannot produce certain types of sentences successfully if they are not explicitly taught about the linguistic conventions of the text-type concerning language features and schematic structures. Therefore, making this convention known by student writers; especially in the first stage of the teaching module with certain types of text are essential duty from the teacher based on genre. The learning process is carried out in the learning cycle which consists of three phases, namely, "sample expert" text modeling, negotiation with texts with teachers, and independent text construction by individual students (Cope and Kalantzis, 1993) [14].

2.2 Teaching Grammar through Genre-Based Approach

Language is viewed as more of a resource for producing meanings than a strict system of grammatical rules and forms. It is a system of choices that allows language users to express social functions and interact with other users of the same language. Therefore, teachers need to build an understanding of the context used to discuss meanings that include culture, time, place, etc., discussing grammatical patterns that arise, and discussing the dominant vocabulary used in conversation. With this process, learners or community can relate it to previous experiences and knowledge. According to this framework, a genre is a "staged, goal-oriented social process" [6] that uses language to achieve social functions in daily contexts. Any social context can be activated some texts that enable language users to perform various social functions. This capacity was called "generic structure potential" [10]. More important, the motivation towards the development of genres in SFL was primarily pedagogical; this can be used as a tool to help instructors in teach writing to be more effective. Regarding the genre as a model of teaching and learning in detail and the more comprehensive way in which it is done [15]. They use the term 'cyclic strategic' to define and stages of teaching and learning writing through a genre-based approach. They also suggest three steps, which must be followed and implemented during the teaching and learning process. The three stages are a) modeling a text, b) joint construction of a text, and c) independent construction of a text. They then, explain each stage has some practical steps to follow systematically.

1) Modeling a text

In shaping a text, there are four concrete steps, which must be implemented during the teaching and learning process. The four practical steps are:

- a. The teacher chooses a specific type of genre writing to develop the classroom activities. In this case, the kind of genre must match with the student needs and market needs where they will work later on.

- b. The teacher and the students discuss the text genre by modeling and deconstruction or even manipulating the text.
- c. The students are directed and situated to know and understand the function of the text, the communicative purpose of the text. Take for example the genre procedure writing-the function of procedure and the meaning of writing procedure.
- d. The students then, study the vocabulary usages of a particular genre procedure, grammatical or structural patterns of the process, and then the students practice the method if necessary.

2) Joint construction

Joint negotiation of the text focuses on the stage when students do the class action, which manipulate relevant language forms. It enhances a negotiating process in both ways between the teacher and the students. It involves reading, research, and disseminating information, and the text of the genre is dependent on those activities. The independent construction of texts is the final phase; in which learners produce actual texts through activities such as choosing a topic, researching, and writing. Proponents such as Kay and Dudley Evans (1998) [16] have argued that the genre approach is more useful for learners to advance their writing skills in a second language than the process approach since the model helps free students from their severe worries overwriting. In joint construction stage, the students start to do something more practical and operational dealing with writing. However, their work of genre writing is not writing at all because they modify and manipulate the text given. The students are still guided and helped by the teacher before they become the independent writer of a specific genre taught and learned. There are three practical steps how to join construction stage is developed and implemented.

- a. The students reconstruct the confident genre writing given. In this case, the student may revise and paraphrase the vocabulary usage, the grammatical patterns, and textual devices if necessary by their own words.
- b. The teacher continuously guides the students to discuss and order the students to remember so that they understand well about the genre type given.
- c. Before going forward to stage three, the independent construction of the text, stage modeling text and joint assembly are essential to review.

3) Independent construction of a text

By having prior comprehension and experiences of stage one and stage two, the students are ordered to write a specific type of genre as what they have learned before. This includes the step when they first begin to build sentences. The student writes a given genre type independently. In this case, the teacher must be sure that the students understand the features of a specific genre such as the communicative purpose, structure element of the text, grammatical patterns usage, proper vocabulary usage, and textual devices as well. Throughout this three stages, students might be able to construct better of the sentences they have in class. To have a vivid pictorial flow chart of cyclic teaching and learning of writing through genre-based approach, Hyland (2003) as quoted in Dirgeyasa (2014) [17] draws as it is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Rothery's Model of genre teaching and learning cycle.

In line with the above model of genre teaching and learning cycle, (Rothery, 1996) in Firkin, Forey, and Sengupta, (2007) [15] also proposes the model of the genre of teaching and learning cycle. He draws the teaching and learning cycle model is similar to Hyland, but his model is more comprehensive and operational to do. It looks more complicated than Hyland's model to do as shown by Figure 2. This figure shows how Rothery's model of genre teaching and learning cycle is designed and developed.

Figure 2. Rothery's model of genre teaching and learning cycle is designed and developed (after Firkin et al. 2007).

By this model, the student can learn how to construct the sentences then write indeed gradually and systematically. This can help them to write by comparing and contrasting their previous work in building sentences to the final act of writing. By doing so, the students know the strengths and the weaknesses of their writing. In line with the student process of learning, genre-based approach to teaching and learning writing, this model of teaching and learning writing helps to raise the students' awareness of particular areas of difficulties while at the same time it promotes learner autonomy [18].

3 METHODOLOGY

This research is classified into a qualitative approach by using the phenomenological method. According to Van Manen (1990:12) [18] "Phenomenology is both the description of the lived-through quality of lived experience and the description of the meaning of the expressions of lived experience". Moreover, Sukmadinata (2008:63) [20] states "phenomenological research is the research which collects the data concerning with the concept, opinion, conviction, attitude, evaluation and giving the meaning to the situation or the life experiences". The description of meaning is a mediated expression and is more interpretive.

3.1 Participants

Twenty-seven of class XI Language and Culture took part in this study. The activity was conducted outside their regular-class hours on 27 September 2018 to offer the student participants a lot of opportunities to practice more in constructing sentences. Meanwhile, the writing skills are still regarded as the critical elements in the mainstream English course books in the regular-class hours at school.

3.2 Data Collection and Analysis

Research data was collected through students' work in constructing sentences.

Students' task

The results from students were the ones written about "The event that they had done in the past, the fact that happening from the past up to present, and the event that will be completed in the future. The analysis of sentences was based on the evaluative criteria of the language features on the recount genre. These include: focusing on the main specific human participants, process types (i.e. material process, relational process and mental process) and the past, present, future tense of verbs, and circumstantial adverbs of time. To enhance the validity of the study, the students' written task was used as core data to check the development of students' progress in constructing English grammar.

4 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

In the learning process, students look more active in applying the joint construction of the text stage by brainstorming about what they have done and what they will do in the future as a topic on the structure of the text. Students seemed more enthusiastic in expressing the ideas to make long simple sentences, due to issues that they have been more familiar. Besides, in performing the stages of modeling and deconstructing the text, students appear to focus more detail on the structure of the sentence and the form of time used in the sentences.

Table 1. Language Features of Students' Task

Language Features			
Main Participants	Process Types	Past, Present, Future Perfect Tense	Circumstantial Adverbs of Time
27	77.78	80.37	77.78

Table 1 indicates that more than 70% of the students were successful in identifying the language features of their task in building sentences. The students make sentences not only for

answering the questions, but they are also directed to analyze the context of the situation or time they write for. Therefore, they can write a simple sentence using correct grammar and vocabulary by contextualizing the time order into their sentences. In other words, in the sequences of event phases, students demonstrated their proper comprehension and excellent accomplishment of typical features of sentence structure by deploying appropriate circumstantial adverbs of time and adequate tenses (past perfect, present perfect, and future perfect tense) of verbs. Moreover, they were also successful in deploying proper linguistic resources by using a variety of process types such as Material process, Relational Process, Mental Process across the schematic structure of their work. In short, it was evident from their sentences that majority of the students comprehend over the features in constructing the sentence. Students at SMA Negeri 1 Kota Ternate met the common grounds in constructing the sentence using past perfect, present perfect, and future perfect. Therefore, a genre-based approach is suitable in incorporating into language teaching because it enhances the cultural communicative activities or practices that construct meanings within a given context. Besides, a genre-based approach is highly structured with some constraints concerning context, form, and linguistic features due to the context play a significant role in framing the structure and the function of each genre. The integration of the genre-based approach into teaching English grammar motivates the need for early inclusion of highly functional genres in English instructional textbooks and materials that are used in Indonesia.

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5 CONCLUSIONS

From Findings and discussion, it can be concluded that (1) A genre-based approach can be applied into language teaching because it encourages the students' practices or learning activities in class that construct meanings within a given context., (2) A genre-based approach is highly structured with several constraints regarding context, form, and linguistic features because the context plays a vital role in framing the structure and function of every genre.

REFERENCES

- [1] Crawford J., (2002), The role of materials in the language classroom: Finding the balance, In Jack C.
- [2] Gilmore A., (2007), Authentic materials and authenticity in foreign language learning, *Language Teaching*, 40(2), pp. 97-118.
- [3] Mishan F., (2005), *Designing Authenticity into Language Learning Materials*, Bristol, Intellect.

- [4] Badger R., White G., (2000), A Process Genre Approach to Teaching Writing, *ELT Journal*, 54(2), pp. 153-160.
- [5] Halliday M., (1985), *Spoken and Written Language*, Geelong, Deakin University Press.
- [6] Martin J., (1992), *English Text: System and Structure*, Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- [7] Hammond J., Derewianka B., (2001), Genre, In R. Carter & D. Nunan (Eds), *The Cambridge Guide to Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- [8] Muncie, J. (2002). Finding a Place for Grammar in EFL Composition Classes. *EFL Journal*, 56, p. 407-430
- [9] Vygotsky L. S., (1978), *Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Process*, Cambridge, Mass, Havard University Press.
- [10] Hyland K., (2003), *Second Language Writing*, London, Cambridge University Press.
- [11] Reid J., (1995), *Teaching ESL Writing*, Upper Saddle River, NJ: Heinle and Heinle.
- [12] Rothery J., (1996), Making Changes: Developing an Educational Linguistics, In R. Hasan & G. Williams (Eds.), *Literacy in Society*, London: Longman.
- [13] Christie F., (1990), Genre as Social Processes, A plenary Paper Delivered at the Meanjin Reading Council Regional Conference, Brisbane (March, 23-25), pp. 74-78.
- [14] Cope B., Kalantzis M., (1993), Introduction: How a Genre Approach to Literacy can Transform the Way Writing is Taught, In B. Cope & M. Kalantzis (Eds.), *The Powers of Literacy: A genre approach to teaching writing*, London: Falmer Press, pp. 1-21.
- [15] Firkins, Arthur Sengupta, Sima, dan Forey Gail, (2007), Teaching Writing to Low Proficiency EFL Students, *ELT Journal*, 61(4), Oxford University Press, pp. 343-344.
- [16] Kay H., Dudley Evans T, (1998), Genre: What teachers think, *ELT Journal*, 52(4), pp. 308-314.
- [17] Dirgeyasa W. I., (2014), *College Academic Writing: A Genre-Based Perspective*, Medan, Unimed Press.
- [18] Weber J. J. A., (2001), Concordance-and Genre-Informed Approach to ESP Essay Writing, *ELT Journal*, 55(1), pp. 15. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/elt/55.1.14>.
- [19] Van Manen M, (1990), *Researching Lived Experience: Human Science for an Action Sensitive Pedagogy*, New York: SUNY Press.
- [20] Sukmadinata N.S., (2008), *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.